

PTLM selection technical issues (RQ1)			◀ Consumers (%)		Producers (%) ▶		└ Decision-Making & Process			◀ Consumers (%)		Producers (%) ▶	
└ Documentation & Standardization							└ Model Retraining Assessment			0.0%		9.8%	
└ └ Model Documentation Omission			20.8%		6.7%		└ Risk Classification			18.8%		7.8%	
└ └ └ API Configuration Fragmentation			0.0%		3.3%		└ Version-Level Vulnerability Profiling			12.9%		9.8%	
└ Evaluation & Runtime Mismatch							Governance Mechanisms to Improve AI Supply Chain (RQ4)						
└ └ Empirical Verification Discrepancies			22.9%		0.0%		└ Standardized Model Naming Convention [Consumer 25.3% vs Producer 40.0%]						
└ └ └ Compute Infrastructure Bottlenecks			13.5%		6.7%		└ Information Accessibility Optimization			40.0%		65.5%	
└ └ └ Runtime Operational Anomalies			16.7%		3.3%		└ Model Repository Uniformity			56.0%		14.5%	
└ Integration & Deployment Friction							└ Workflow Automation			4.0%		16.4%	
└ └ Deployment Environment Incompatibility			9.4%		55.0%		└ Supply Chain Burden Analysis			0.0%		3.6%	
└ └ └ Hardware Architecture Mismatch			10.4%		16.7%		└ Enforced Semantic Versioning [Consumer 11.6% vs Producer 38.0%]						
└ Maintenance & Provenance Risks							└ Lifecycle Tracking			83.3%		57.7%	
└ └ Data and Codebase Opacity			6.2%		0.0%		└ Model Repository Uniformity			16.7%		19.2%	
└ └ └ Runtime Execution Volatility			0.0%		8.3%		└ Model Trustworthiness			0.0%		7.7%	
Coping with Missing Documentation (RQ2)							└ Lineage Auditing			0.0%		3.8%	
└ Community Engagement & Social Signals							└ Information Accessibility Optimization			0.0%		3.8%	
└ └ Community Activity Auditing			11.6%		0.0%		└ Workflow Automation			0.0%		7.7%	
└ └ └ Upstream Issue Escalation			6.3%		0.0%		└ Visual Lineage Graph [Consumer 15.8% vs Producer 34.0%]						
└ Cross-Platform Triangulation & Search							└ Lineage Auditing			77.8%		69.2%	
└ └ Information Triangulation			44.2%		0.0%		└ Information Accessibility Optimization			22.2%		5.1%	
└ └ └ Platform UI Navigation			2.1%		0.0%		└ Model Trustworthiness			0.0%		5.1%	
└ Empirical Verification & Sandbox Testing							└ Workflow Automation			0.0%		10.3%	
└ └ Empirical Functional Testing			23.2%		0.0%		└ Risk Auditing			0.0%		10.3%	
└ └ └ Iterative Model Selection			2.1%		0.0%		└ AI Bill of Materials (AIBOM) Generation Tool [Consumer 8.4% vs Producer 0.0%]						
└ Model Abandonment & Substitution							└ Information Accessibility Optimization			44.4%		0.0%	
└ └ Model Switching			9.5%		0.0%		└ Workflow Automation			22.2%		0.0%	
└ └ └ Speculative Implementation			1.1%		0.0%		└ Lineage Auditing			22.2%		0.0%	
Reasons for Lineage Tracing (RQ3)							└ Supply Chain Burden Analysis			11.1%		0.0%	
└ Risk & Compliance							└ Automatic Model Metadata Prefilling [Consumer 16.8% vs Producer 30.0%]						
└ └ Legal Compliance			13.7%		30.3%		└ Workflow Automation			33.3%		31.8%	
└ └ └ Security Risk Assessment			9.8%		0.0%		└ Lineage Auditing			8.3%		18.2%	
└ Provenance & Reproducibility							└ Model Repository Uniformity			4.2%		0.0%	
└ └ Lineage Validation			11.8%		24.2%		└ Information Accessibility Optimization			50.0%		50.0%	
└ └ └ Provenance Awareness			0.0%		15.2%		└ Supply Chain Burden Analysis			4.2%		0.0%	
└ Model Quality & Reliability							└ Configuration Schema Validation [Consumer 10.5% vs Producer 4.0%]						
└ └ Data Bias Awareness			17.6%		0.0%		└ Model Repository Uniformity			100.0%		100.0%	
└ └ └ Reliability Evaluation			17.6%		12.1%		└ Dependency Disclosure Requirement [Consumer 27.4% vs Producer 28.0%]						
└ Engineering & Workflow							└ Lineage Auditing			25.0%		63.0%	
└ └ Optimize Model Integration			7.8%		12.1%		└ Model Trustworthiness			52.5%		29.6%	
└ └ └ Improve Development Efficiency			7.8%		0.0%		└ Model Repository Uniformity			2.5%		0.0%	
└ Debugging & Troubleshooting							└ Information Accessibility Optimization			5.0%		0.0%	
└ └ Model Debugging			7.8%		6.1%		└ Workflow Automation			15.0%		3.7%	
└ └ └ Resolving Inconsistency			5.9%		0.0%		└ Risk Auditing			0.0%		3.7%	
Lineage Tracing Methods (RQ3)							└ Mandatory Adoption of the SPDX 3.0 AI Profile [Consumer 4.2% vs Producer 4.0%]						
└ Documentation and Metadata Inspection							└ Workflow Automation			0.0%		50.0%	
└ └ Configuration Auditing			13.6%		23.8%		└ Supply Chain Burden Analysis			33.3%		0.0%	
└ └ └ Documentation Examination			22.7%		26.2%		└ Model Repository Uniformity			66.7%		50.0%	
└ Platform and Tool-Based Tracing							└ Hugging Face Platform-Level Badges [Consumer 12.6% vs Producer 26.0%]						
└ └ Automate Lineage Extraction			9.1%		4.8%		└ Model Trustworthiness			41.7%		75.0%	
└ └ └ Lineage Tooling			13.6%		14.3%		└ Lineage Auditing			16.7%		25.0%	
└ Repository and Version Tracking							└ Information Accessibility Optimization			41.7%		0.0%	
└ └ Historical Version Analysis			0.0%		7.1%		└ Single Hugging Face Repository Requirement [Consumer 22.1% vs Producer 12.0%]						
└ └ └ Inspect Repository Metadata			4.5%		4.8%		└ Model Repository Uniformity			66.7%		50.0%	
└ Multi-Source Verification and Testing							└ Information Accessibility Optimization			33.3%		0.0%	
└ └ Artifact Feature Comparison			9.1%		4.8%		└ Workflow Automation			0.0%		50.0%	
└ └ └ External Cross-Referencing			27.3%		9.5%		└ Mandatory Model Card Template [Consumer 44.2% vs Producer 30.0%]						
└ └ └ Manual Documentation Review			0.0%		4.8%		└ Lineage Auditing			20.6%		28.6%	
Model Security Flaw Identification (RQ3)							└ Model Repository Uniformity			36.5%		36.7%	
└ Empirical Testing & Evaluation							└ Model Trustworthiness			15.9%		4.1%	
└ └ Behavioral Assessment			22.4%		27.5%		└ Lifecycle Tracking			1.6%		0.0%	
└ └ └ Component Auditing			0.0%		11.8%		└ Model Capability Assessment			0.0%		6.1%	
└ Dependency Tracing & Impact Analysis							└ Information Accessibility Optimization			19.0%		16.3%	
└ └ Lineage Tracking			11.8%		17.6%		└ Workflow Automation			3.2%		0.0%	
└ └ └ Model Configuration Analysis			7.1%		5.9%		└ Risk Auditing			3.2%		4.1%	
└ Mitigation & Remediation Actions							└ Supply Chain Burden Analysis			0.0%		4.1%	
└ └ Component Isolation Diagnostics			15.3%		0.0%								
└ └ └ Differential Output Analysis			2.4%		0.0%								
└ └ └ Remediation Verification Testing			9.4%		9.8%								